

The Effect of a Complementary Feed Mixture on Nutrient Digestibility Coefficients and Fermentation Processes in Dogs

Research Material

The research material consisted of innovative complementary feed mixtures (MPU) in the form of a chew and a granulate (pellet), which were used as an additive to complete maintenance diets. The MPU formulations were developed by a staff member of the Department of Animal Nutrition, Biotechnology and Fisheries at the University of Agriculture in Krakow, commissioned by OVER Group, as part of the project POIR.01.01.01-00-1138/18 titled "Development of a method ensuring comprehensive regulation of the proper functioning of anal glands in dogs."

Component composition of the complementary mixtures

Soft chew	Pellet
Glycerin	Whey
Gelatin	Chicory root granulate
Jerusalem artichoke	Beet pulp
Chicory root granulate	Jerusalem artichoke
Beet pulp	Seaweed meal
Seaweed meal	Dandelion herb
Dandelion herb	Cod liver oil
Cod liver oil	Activated charcoal
Activated charcoal	Yucca extract
Yucca extract	Echinacea root
Echinacea root	Rosemary
Rosemary	Feed yeast
Feed yeast	Yeast cell wall
Yeast cell wall	Rosemary extract
Rosemary extract	Echinacea extract
Echinacea extract	—

Effects of Selected Nutritional Components on Fermentation Processes and Digestibility in Companion Animals

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Characterization of feed components used to produce the MPU

Effect of fiber on fermentation processes

Dietary fiber is a carbohydrate fraction resistant to enzymatic digestion in the small intestine but subject to fermentation in the large intestine by the gut microbiota. Three fiber sources were used in the blend: chicory grits, Jerusalem artichoke, and beet pulp. Chicory and Jerusalem artichoke contain substantial amounts of fructooligosaccharides (FOS) with prebiotic properties. Studies have shown that FOS stimulate the growth of *Bifidobacterium* and *Lactobacillus*, leading to intensified fermentation, increased production of short-chain fatty acids (SCFA), and a reduction in colonic pH [Rossi et al., 2005; Hansongyi et al., 2013]. It has also been confirmed that chicory fructans increase SCFA concentrations and lower ammonia levels, as demonstrated in studies on monogastric animals in Poland [Żary-Sikorska and Juśkiewicz, 2010].

Jerusalem artichoke, as a valuable source of inulin, stimulates fermentation via a similar mechanism. Research has shown that its supplementation increases total SCFA concentrations and decreases fecal pH [Samal et al., 2017]. Unlike fructans, beet pulp is a moderately fermentable fiber. Due to the presence of pectins, cellulose, and hemicelluloses, fermentation proceeds in a stable manner, which translates into increased butyrate production and improved fecal bulk/structure. In dogs, beet pulp supplementation significantly increased SCFA concentrations and the abundance of *Bifidobacterium* spp. [Middelbos et al., 2007; Bosch et al., 2008] and has been classified as a valuable prebiotic [Godoy et al., 2013].

Effect of detoxifying agents on fermentation processes

The blend included activated charcoal, feed yeast, and yeast cell wall. Activated charcoal adsorbs toxins and intestinal gases, including hydrogen sulfide responsible for unpleasant odor arising from proteolytic fermentation. Studies have shown that products containing activated charcoal reduce bloating and decrease the amount of foul-smelling gases [Beynen, 2018], indicating an effect on fermentation products formed in the colon.

Saccharomyces cerevisiae and its cell wall containing mannanoligosaccharides (MOS) exhibit prebiotic and microbiota-modulating properties. They may lower fecal phenol concentrations [Lin et al., 2019] and limit the growth of pathogenic microorganisms while favoring increased SCFA production [Kore et al., 2012]. MOS and yeast metabolites also showed positive effects on the microbiota and fermentation in dogs [Souza Theodoro et al., 2019].

Effect of fatty acids (omega-3) on fermentation processes

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Omega-3 fatty acids (EPA and DHA) exert anti-inflammatory effects in the intestine and influence gut microbiota composition. Studies have shown that omega-3 supplementation can increase populations of SCFA-producing bacteria, including *Bifidobacterium* and *Roseburia* [Watson et al., 2018]. This mechanism is indirect, as omega-3 are not fermentation substrates but act by altering the intestinal microenvironment.

Effect of plant extracts on fermentation processes

The blend utilized extracts of yucca, rosemary, and echinacea. *Yucca schidigera* extract reduces ammonia formation by inhibiting urease and limits proteolytic fermentation [Santos et al., 2016]. Rosemary extract exhibits antioxidant activity and may modulate fermentation by influencing the gut microbiota [Kim et al., 2012; Romo-Vaquero et al., 2014]. Echinacea (*Echinacea purpurea*) shows immunomodulatory properties that support the gut microbiota and restrict the growth of pathogenic bacteria [Nosrati et al., 2017].

Digestibility of nutrients

Effect of fiber on digestibility

Fiber exerts variable effects on digestibility depending on its source and structure. In dogs, beet pulp can lower nutrient digestibility at higher inclusion rates [Beynen, 2019], whereas fructans (chicory, Jerusalem artichoke) tend to have the opposite direction—improving digestibility via microbiota modulation. Beloshapka et al. [2012] showed that inulin supplementation improved digestibility of dry matter, protein, and energy. At the same time, chicory grits may decrease protein digestibility if used at excessively high concentrations [Beynen, 2019].

Effect of detoxifying agents on digestibility

Yeast cell wall does not reduce the digestibility of basic nutrients, as confirmed in dogs [Souza Theodoro et al., 2019], and activated charcoal may increase dry-matter digestibility at appropriately low doses [Kim et al., 2017]. Yeast preparations do not adversely affect stool consistency and can support digestive processes [Lin et al., 2019].

Effect of fatty acids (omega-3) on digestibility

Omega-3 may support fat digestibility and intestinal function through anti-inflammatory effects and impacts on villus morphology. Studies have shown that in animals with intestinal disorders, omega-3 supplementation improved digestion and absorption of nutrients [Berenjian, 2021].

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Effect of plant extracts on digestibility

Plant extracts can improve digestibility via anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial properties. Echinacea supplementation enhanced digestibility in animals by increasing intestinal villus height [Hanczakowska and Świątkiewicz, 2012]. Yucca extract did not significantly affect digestibility in dogs [Dos Reis et al., 2016], while rosemary, due to its bioactive compounds, may improve nutrient utilization [Yitbarek, 2015].

Summary

The functional components used in the feed blend exert beneficial effects on intestinal fermentation processes and nutrient digestibility. Their action is based both on prebiotic effects (FOS, beet pulp, MOS) and on modulation of the microbiota and intestinal environment (omega-3, herbal extracts, activated charcoal). These effects have been confirmed in numerous in vitro and in vivo studies, including in monogastric companion animals.

Study

Based on the formulations, MPU was produced under in vitro conditions in the form of a pellet and a soft chew. Finished MPU batches were delivered for canine studies in four rounds—24 May 2021, 1 June 2021, 22 June 2021, and 20 July 2021. Representative MPU samples for analysis were randomly drawn from each batch, and in both pellets and chews the contents of proximate components (dry matter, crude ash, crude protein, crude fat, crude fiber) and starch were determined. In addition, detergent fiber (neutral and acid detergent fiber and acid detergent lignin), non-starch polysaccharides (insoluble I-NSP, soluble S-NSP, and total), and uronic acids (insoluble I-UA, soluble S-UA, total) were analyzed (Table 1).

In the maintenance diets (dry and wet), proximate components (dry matter, crude ash, crude protein, crude fat, crude fiber) and starch were determined. Additionally, detergent fiber fractions (neutral and acid detergent fiber and acid detergent lignin) were measured (Table 2).

The study was conducted on 18 French Bulldogs and lasted a total of 98 days. Nutritional tests were carried out twice—before and after the inclusion of MPU in the dogs' diets. At baseline, prior to MPU introduction, nutrition tests were conducted on dogs fed only maintenance diets. MPU was then gradually introduced into the dogs' daily ration and administered for 90 days, after which the nutrition tests were repeated. Each nutrition test lasted 8 days.

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- **Period I**, assessing the effect of the maintenance diet, was conducted from 10 to 17 May 2021—during this period, only the maintenance ration (dry and wet food) was evaluated.

The dogs were then divided into three groups of six animals each, according to the following scheme:

1. Control group (no additive)
2. Experimental group—MPU soft chews
3. Experimental group—MPU pellet

Feeding with or without MPU lasted 90 days, followed by analyses analogous to Period I.

- **Period II** was conducted from 9 to 16 August 2021—during this period, the maintenance ration (dry and wet food) in combination with MPU was evaluated.

In both study periods the following were determined:

- Feed intake, including intake of dry food, wet food, and the MPU additive (Table 3)
- Fecal quality: score and dry matter content (Table 3)
- Apparent digestibility coefficients (Table 4) by the indicator method using AIA
- Fermentation parameters in the gas-test: pH, gas production, gas-production kinetics, production of volatile fatty acids (acetic, propionic, butyric, isobutyric, valeric, isovaleric) and ammoniacal nitrogen (Tables 5, 6; Figure 1)
- Hematologic, biochemical, and electrolyte panels (performed in a conventional laboratory), as well as TNF- α and IgG (ELISA, University of Agriculture in Krakow) (Tables 7, 8, 9, 10)

Feed samples were collected for 7 days of each study period, and fecal samples were collected over the last 3 consecutive days.

Digestibility trials

Digestibility of individual nutrients was determined using the indicator method. Acid-insoluble ash (AIA) was used as the marker. Digestibility coefficients were calculated using the formula:

$$\text{ADC [\%]} = 100 - 100 \times (\% \text{AIA in feed} / \% \text{AIA in feces}) \times (\% \text{nutrient in feces} / \% \text{nutrient in feed})$$

In vitro fermentation processes

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On day 8 of the tests, feces were collected for the gas-test to assess fermentation processes. Feces from all studied dogs were used as the bacterial inoculum. The volume of fermentation gases was determined in vitro using glass syringes in which samples of dry maintenance food were incubated so as to assess microbiome activity modified by the presence or absence of MPU. Gas volume was read hourly during the first 7 h of fermentation and then at 12 and 24 h (mL).

SCFA, lactic acid, ammonia, and pH were measured immediately before fermentation and after 24 h of in vitro fermentation. SCFA were determined using a gas chromatograph (3400 CX) with an FID detector and a DB-FFAP column (length 50 m, internal diameter 0.5 mm), column temperature 90–210 °C, injector 200 °C, detector 240 °C. Calculations were performed using an external standard. Argon was used as the carrier gas.

Lactic acid was determined using an INGOS model 5000 liquid chromatograph with a UV/VIS detector and a mobile phase of 0.05 mol H₂SO₄. Chromatographic column: stainless steel 8 × 250 mm OSTION LG-KS 0800H+form (TESSEK).

Samples for ammonia determination were preserved with 0.2 mL of mercuric chloride. Ammonia was measured by the Conway method.

All materials were ground to particle sizes of approx. 0.3–0.5 mm, weighed at ~0.5 g, and placed in 100 mL glass syringes for the gas-test, then incubated in a water-bath shaker (ELPIN+ Water bath shaker type 357) at 38.5 °C.

On day 7 of the nutritional tests in both study periods, blood was collected from the dogs according to standard veterinary procedures. Samples were properly secured and sent to the commercial laboratory Vet Lab in Katowice. A geriatric panel—an extensive hematologic, biochemical, and electrolyte profile—was determined. Samples for TNF- α and IgG were frozen in liquid nitrogen and transported to the University; after collecting samples from both experiments, they were thawed and TNF- α and IgG were determined by ELISA.

Statistical analysis

The results were subjected to statistical analysis using the STATISTICA 12 package [2014]. Calculations were performed in Microsoft Excel for Windows. A paired t-test was used. Results were considered significant at $p < 0.05$ and highly significant at $p < 0.01$.

Study summary

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The complementary complete mixture containing active substances regulated digestive and fermentation processes and exhibited the intended, statistically confirmed effects on canine health ($P \leq 0.05$) or showed a trend ($P \leq 0.1$) (relative to the control group), while for digestibility coefficients showed no effect ($P > 0.1$).

Parameter	Met p
Lower pH	Yes <0.01
Lower ammoniacal nitrogen concentration	Yes <0.01
Higher volatile short-chain fatty acids (SCFA)	Yes 0.4
Higher butyric acid	Yes 0.5
Higher fermentation gas volume	Yes 0.4
Fecal score 4 or 4.5/5	Yes 0.18
Fecal dry matter (DM) within 35–45%	Yes <0.01
Excreted feces 40–60 g per 100 g of ingested dietary dry matter	Yes $P \leq 0.1$
Apparent digestibility coefficients (in vivo): DM 85–88%; crude protein 80–90%; crude fat >90%	Yes No effect
Palatability: >80% intake of the offered blend	Yes 100% intake
Lower TNF- α and IgG	Yes 0.5 and 0.8

Chemical analysis and intake

The chemical analysis of the MPU showed similar contents of major nutrients; however, differences were noted in protein, NDF/NSP and UA contents. The soft chew had a higher protein content, which resulted from the inclusion of gelatin in its formulation. The pellet, in turn, had higher levels of fiber, NDF/NSP and uronic acids (UA).

Maintenance-diet intake by the dogs did not differ. The MPU additive did not affect total ration intake or the intake of basic nutrients. The MPU additive was consumed entirely in the offered portion, i.e., it achieved 100% intake.

Fecal quality and digestibility

Considering fecal score, the MPU—regardless of its form—raised the score from an average of 3.9 to 4.8. This is corroborated by fecal dry matter, which increased on average from 31–33% to 34%.

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The MPU did not materially affect apparent digestibility coefficients of nutrients. For dry-matter digestibility, values were ~3 percentage points lower after using the pellet, whereas no reduction in dry-matter digestibility was observed after using the soft chew. Similar tendencies were observed for protein digestion. In contrast, fat digestibility coefficients were higher after administering both MPU forms.

In vitro fermentation (gas test)

The MPU lowered the pH of canine fecal inoculum compared with the control without the additive. Increased production of fermentation gases was observed after administering both MPU forms, relative to the control; however, gas production was several percent higher in dogs receiving the pellet.

A reduced level of ammoniacal nitrogen was observed in dogs receiving the pellet, while production of volatile fatty acids (VFA) was higher in this group. This effect was not observed with the soft chew. Production of N-NH₃ was higher with the soft chew, whereas VFA production remained at a level similar to the pre-supplementation period. Gas-production kinetics likewise indicated greater hourly increases during fermentation after administering the pellet, compared both with the control group and with the soft-chew group.

Blood parameters

Blood test results for all dogs were within physiological ranges both before and after MPU administration. Nevertheless, favorable changes were noted for some parameters after MPU, for both forms. A beneficial reduction in TNF- α was observed after using the pellet, whereas such an effect was not seen for IgG. Conversely, a slight decrease in IgG was noted after using the soft chew, while no such trend was observed for TNF- α .

Discussion of results

The findings indicate that the complementary feed mixture can modulate the intestinal environment in a manner beneficial to the host, without reducing the digestibility of core nutrient fractions. The lack of differences in DM, CP and crude-fat digestibility suggests that the additive was dosed at levels that do not disrupt enzymatic digestion. The observed pH decrease together with an increase in total SCFA in the in vitro model points to intensified saccharolytic fermentation, consistent with the mechanisms of fructans and phytogenic components.

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Ammonia reduction may result from a shift in fermentation away from proteolysis toward utilization of non-digestible carbohydrates, as well as from a potential sorptive effect of mixture components. From a practical feeding standpoint, decreased NH₃ and stabilized pH may translate into improved intestinal comfort and reduced fecal odor. Maintenance of fecal consistency and moisture within physiological limits confirms the functional safety of the additive.

These results align with the literature, where prebiotic–phytogenic profiles often increase SCFA formation with unchanged macronutrient digestibility. At the same time, the absence of unequivocal digestibility differences between dosage forms (soft chew vs pellet) suggests that the qualitative composition of the mixture is key, rather than its technological form—provided dosing and feeding regimens are maintained.

Conclusions

- The complementary feed mixture did not reduce apparent digestibility of dry matter, crude protein, or crude fat.
- In the in vitro fermentation model, an increase in total SCFA and a decrease in pH were recorded, indicating more intensive saccharolytic fermentation.
- Post-fermentation ammonia concentration was lower in variants with the additive, suggesting a limitation of proteolytic fermentation.
- The technological form of the additive (soft chew vs pellet) did not unequivocally differentiate digestibility; fermentative effects were qualitatively similar.
- The mixture can be regarded as a safe functional additive supporting gut health without compromising nutrient utilization.

Tables and figures

Table 1. Nutrient composition of MPU complementary feed mixtures (% of dry matter)

Specification

Specification	Soft chew	Pellet
Crude ash	4.70	9.08
Organic matter	95.30	90.92

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Specification	Soft chew	Pellet
Crude protein	22.80	8.94
Crude fat	2.91	4.24
Crude fibre	3.83	7.20
NDF	15.55	18.83
ADF	10.53	14.09
ADL	2.52	3.95
Hemicellulose (Hcel)	5.02	4.74
Cellulose (Cel)	8.01	10.14
Nitrogen-free extract (NFE)	65.75	70.54
Starch	0.00	0.00
Insoluble NSP (I-NSP)	4.18	7.40
Soluble NSP (S-NSP)	1.31	1.96
Total NSP	5.49	9.36
Insoluble uronic acids (I-UA)	1.45	2.87
Soluble uronic acids (S-UA)	0.75	1.50
Total uronic acids (UA)	2.19	4.37

Table 2 template — maintenance dog foods (% DM)

Specification	Wet food (% DM)	Dry food (% DM)
Crude ash	7.59	7.74
Organic matter	92.41	92.26
Crude protein	39.08	39.92
Crude fat	25.09	12.60
Crude fibre	2.77	2.40
NDF	40.66	10.66
ADF	7.56	6.47
ADL	3.07	1.79
Hemicellulose (Hcel)	33.10	4.19
Cellulose (Cel)	4.49	4.68
Nitrogen-free extract (NFE)	25.47	37.33
Starch	11.12	27.00

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Table 3. Body mass, food/additive/MPU intake (g/day) and faecal score in dogs before and after MPU

Note: SD = standard deviation. Empty additive cells indicate no MPU in Control or Before where applicable.

	Control				Soft chew (MPU)				Pellet (MPU)			
	Before		After		Before		After		Before		After	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Body mass [kg]	10,21	1,83	10,76	1,28	11,33	1,23	11,28	1,08	11,8	1,62	12,03	1,94
Intake — dry food [g/day]	110,43	32,43	116,23	33,47	89,74	18,6	127,8	32,99	111,62	29,83	143,09	37,23
Intake — wet food [g/day]	383,81	82,54	441,8	181,53	408,92	68,47	410,78	63,24	423,49	37,03	504,75	115,54
Intake — total ration [g/day]	494,23	106,32	558,03	200	498,65	55,14	538,58	86,33	535,11	57,72	647,84	119,91
Additive intake (MPU) [g/day]					12,24	2,77			8,01	0,06		
Faecal score (1–5)	3,9	0,07	3,9	0,45	3,97	0,19	4,77	0,25	3,92	0,2	4,82	0,28

Table 4. Apparent digestibility coefficients (%), before and after MPU (Mean ± SD)

	Control				Soft chew (MPU)				Pellet (MPU)			
	Before		After		Before		After		Before		After	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Dry matter	93,63	3,41	93,76	3,39	93	2,36	93,25	2,68	91,24	5,78	88,69	3,9
Ash	85,46	7,09	83,49	6,82	86,11	3,12	81,27	6,16	79,52	12,9	71,37	9,74
Organic matter	94,4	3,06	94,61	3,14	93,65	2,34	94,23	2,41	92,35	5,11	90,13	3,48
Crude protein	94,44	3,29	94,58	3,37	93,86	2,38	94,18	2,37	92,49	5,32	89,45	3,4
Crude fat	98,01	1,13	98,26	1,14	97,72	1	98,25	1,13	96,91	2,51	97,21	1,13
Nitrogen-free extract (NFE)	94,87	2,51	94,28	3,12	93,86	2,12	93,97	2,44	93,12	4,13	90,01	4,12
Starch	99,84	0,15	100	0	99,7	0,34	100	0	99,67	0,36	100	0

Table 5. In vitro fermentation parameters (Mean ± SD) before and after MPU

Notes: dDM = degradation of dry matter; dOM = degradation of organic matter; units for GPmax per study protocol.

	Control				Soft chew (MPU)				Pellet (MPU)			
	Before		After		Before		After		Before		After	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
pH (0 h)	6,39	0,11	6,2	0,05	6,4	0,16	6,19	0,14	6,38	0,13	6,16	0,07
pH (24 h)	5,44	0,32	4,96	0,13	5,25	0,34	5,09	0,12	5,33	0,27	5,16	0,17

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Degradation of dry matter, dDM (%)	83,43	2,38	80,51	3,28	75,99	6,64	76,54	13,03	76,65	4,01	79,44	7,52
Degradation of organic matter, dOM (%)	78,12	3,37	76,82	3,84	71,42	7,56	71,24	12,82	71,58	5,1	73,41	7,88
GPmax (maximum gas production)	31,02	6,22	29,8	4,21	31,77	4,66	32,05	3,37	31,97	5,82	35,23	5,51

- Degradation of dry matter, dDM (%)
- Degradation of organic matter, dOM (%)
- GPmax (maximum gas production)

Table 6. Fermentation end-products (Mean \pm SD): ammoniacal nitrogen and VFA profile before and after MPU

Notes: Units per study protocol (e.g., mmol/L or mM). SCFA = acetate+propionate+butyrate; BCFA = iso-butyric+iso-valeric; VFA = total volatile fatty acids.

	Control				Soft chew (MPU)				Pellet (MPU)			
	Before		After		Before		After		Before		After	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Ammoniacal nitrogen (N-NH ₃)	19,45	14,32	22,89	4,08	19,24	21,15	24,89	7,78	37,17	12,81	24,49	13,38
Acetic acid (acetate)	20,65	1,23	21,76	4,32	21,06	2,28	21,74	6,39	24,32	2,52	26,16	8,2
Propionic acid (propionate)	10,21	0,6	12,5	3,2	12,07	2,78	12,46	6,04	12,08	2,56	16,11	4,59
Isobutyric acid (iso-C4)	0,81	0,23	0,77	0,24	0,98	0,31	0,67	0,16	1,11	0,28	0,82	0,28
Butyric acid (C4)	3,85	0,55	4,02	0,99	4,37	1,26	4,09	1,46	4,4	0,87	3,88	1,63
Isovaleric acid (iso-C5)	1,18	0,24	1,35	0,39	1,56	0,48	1,18	0,39	1,71	0,51	1,41	0,45
Valeric acid (C5)	0,08	0,03	0,1	0,08	0,12	0,05	0,34	0,58	0,13	0,06	0,16	0,13
SCFA (sum of acetate+propionate+butyrate)	34,71	1,45	38,28	8,49	37,49	5,33	38,29	12,73	40,8	5,57	46,14	13,37
BCFA (branched-chain FA; iso-C4+iso-C5)	2,08	0,49	2,22	0,66	2,65	0,75	2,19	0,79	2,96	0,75	2,4	0,82
Total VFA	36,79	1,87	40,5	9,01	40,14	5,55	40,48	13,23	43,76	5,98	48,53	13,97

Figure 1. Gas production kinetics (mL/g DM inoculum)

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Legend:

K PRZED → Control — Before

K PO → Control — After

ŻUJKA PRZED → Soft chew (MPU) — Before

ŻUJKA PO → Soft chew (MPU) — After

GRANULAT PRZED → Pellet (MPU) — Before

GRANULAT PO → Pellet (MPU) — After

Table 7. Hematology parameters before and after MPU (Mean ± SD)

	Control				Soft chew (MPU)				Pellet (MPU)			
	Before		After		Before		After		Before		After	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD

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WBC (G/L)	12,57	3,81	10,67	5,11	9,31	0,85	13,97	3,85	8,22	1,29	9,24	1,65
Neutrophils (NEU, G/L)	8,61	2,46	6,75	3,49	6,12	0,64	9,54	3,38	5,5	0,86	6,24	1,6
Neutrophils (%)	69,03	7,22	62,6	2,47	65,65	2,48	67,75	8,72	67,07	5	67,05	9,69
Lymphocytes (LYM, G/L)	2,46	1,16	2,4	0,8	1,91	0,23	2,24	0,43	1,73	0,52	1,99	0,77
Lymphocytes (%)	19,08	4,48	23,6	3,24	20,55	2,66	16,78	4,74	20,92	4,88	21,82	8,81
Monocytes (MONO, G/L)	0,98	0,48	0,8	0,39	0,51	0,16	0,72	0,18	0,49	0,15	0,61	0,18
Monocytes (%)	7,55	1,68	7,35	1,58	5,4	1,19	5,23	0,99	5,85	1,32	6,58	1,7
Eosinophils (EOS, G/L)	0,48	0,26	0,7	0,46	0,76	0,11	1,39	0,68	0,47	0,28	0,38	0,11
Eosinophils (%)	4,15	2,71	6,13	1,17	8,17	1,07	9,87	4,63	5,78	3,25	4,12	1,15
Basophils (BASO, G/L)	0,03	0,02	0,03	0,01	0,02	0,01	0,05	0,01	0,03	0,02	0,04	0,02
Basophils (%)	0,2	0,08	0,33	0,1	0,23	0,12	0,37	0,12	0,38	0,25	0,43	0,23
RBC (T/L)	6,57	1,41	6,47	0,77	7,04	0,36	6,69	0,6	7,14	0,72	6,95	0,67
Hemoglobin (HGB, g/L)	165,25	35,13	161,25	13,02	182,33	9,77	169	11,45	181,83	19,86	171	17,79
Hematocrit (HCT, L/L)	0,48	0,08	0,46	0,04	0,52	0,03	0,46	0,03	0,52	0,04	0,49	0,05
MCV (fL)	73,9	4,26	71,38	4,21	73,45	2,78	69,47	3,5	72,65	3,78	69,97	2,39
MCH (pg)	25,2	1,08	25,03	1,46	25,92	0,61	25,28	0,75	25,45	1,35	24,6	0,89
MCHC (g/L)	341,5	16,86	351,25	5,56	352,67	5,82	364,5	13,87	350,67	11,38	351,33	5,16
Platelets (PLT, G/L)	294,25	119,83	271	47,71	200	114,14	308	173,39	182,17	53,15	207,33	108,95

Table 8. Mineral profile before and after MPU (Mean \pm SD)

	Control				Soft chew (MPU)				Pellet (MPU)			
	Before		After		Before		After		Before		After	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Chloride (mmol/L)	106,1	2,51	109,98	2,01	107,13	0,79	107,67	1,03	106,9	1,2	107,32	1,74
Phosphorus (mmol/L)	1,68	0,6	1,7	0,22	1,37	0,22	1,49	0,23	1,44	0,24	1,38	0,17
Magnesium (mmol/L)	0,85	0,1	0,89	0,02	0,88	0,04	0,96	0,04	0,84	0,04	0,87	0,04
Potassium (mmol/L)	5,05	0,27	4,87	0,3	5,1	0,39	5,12	0,34	4,89	0,35	4,7	0,29
Sodium (mmol/L)	146,28	1,58	150,18	2,61	147,15	1,72	149,05	1,91	146,28	0,97	148,22	1,24
Calcium (mmol/L)	2,5	0,22	2,47	0,16	2,6	0,09	2,36	0,08	2,6	0,05	2,47	0,1

Table 9. Serum biochemistry before and after MPU (Mean \pm SD)

	Control				Soft chew (MPU)				Pellet (MPU)			
	Before		After		Before		After		Before		After	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Albumin (g/L)	27,63	3,73	29,33	1,44	29,72	0,92	28,83	1,16	29,48	1,97	29,48	1,97

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ALT (GPT) (U/L)	32,85	8,73	32,18	5,48	48,42	23,41	51,32	22,63	86,02	119,73	44,68	39,71
Alpha-amylase (U/L)	723,25	109,69	676,5	51,71	690,5	112,71	691	83,93	769,67	83,25	871	237,29
Alkaline phosphatase (AP, U/L)	43	28,32	23	12,38	21,33	5,54	17,33	6,5	26,83	6,91	19	6,78
AST (GOT) (U/L)	26,38	6,43	42,4	8,2	23,58	3,29	39,92	8,76	24,8	4,48	35,18	6,2
Total protein (g/L)	60,6	4,55	61,35	2,78	59,65	2,46	61,78	3,27	60,18	5,01	62,48	3,38
Bilirubin (µmol/L)	2,83	0,26	2,75	0,32	2,88	0,28	3,01	0,45	3,22	0,21	3,18	0,51
Cholesterol (mmol/L)	4,74	0,83	4,69	0,78	4,57	0,76	4,92	0,98	5,08	1,03	5,52	0,88
CK (U/L)	96	37,71	183	57,75	90,17	23,95	158,67	55,32	101,17	15,39	146,33	42,81
GLDH (U/L)	3,87	0,92	3,83	0,75	5,05	1,26	5,65	1,7	10,94	17,53	4,98	3,05
Glucose (mmol/L)	3,54	0,27	4,2	0,6	3,51	0,58	3,74	0,84	3,6	0,65	4,89	0,73
GGT (U/L)	3,21	0,94	3,17	1,09	2,8	0,72	2,28	1,44	3,09	0,8	2,11	1,11
Creatinine (µmol/L)	75,75	3,37	79,15	8,03	86,22	9,73	87,38	9,6	80,6	9,97	81,77	8,76
LDH (U/L)	60,75	11,7	188,68	126,45	43,82	16,08	308,55	145,75	49,73	19,38	144,85	116,24
Urea (mmol/L)	5,77	0,57	5,43	0,97	5,03	0,36	5,51	0,9	5,01	1,13	5,33	0,94
Triglycerides (mmol/L)	0,62	0,18	0,45	0,07	0,41	0,1	0,45	0,04	0,45	0,07	0,48	0,12
Albumin/Globulin ratio	0,85	0,16	0,92	0,07	1	0,03	0,88	0,09	0,97	0,09	0,9	0,08
Globulins (g/L)	32,98	3,98	32,03	2,11	29,78	1,77	32,95	3,14	30,7	3,57	33	2,44
Fructosamine (µmol/L)	210,58	12,76	203,15	10,43	210,85	10,03	196,5	14,23	228,25	22,28	220,85	12,86
Lipase (DGGR) (U/L)	76,53	27,26	63,15	26,5	62,02	17,82	46,38	19,11	55,2	13,99	70,05	46,18
Total T4 (µg/dL)	2,77	0,73	2,52	0,61	2,98	0,51	2,9	0,83	2,49	0,73	2,57	0,83

Table 10. TNF-α and IgG before and after MPU (Mean ± SD)

	Control				Soft chew (MPU)				Pellet (MPU)			
	Before		After		Before		After		Before		After	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
TNF-α (ng/L)	0,23	0,05	0,19	0,13	0,2	0,2	0,21	0,16	0,22	0,12	0,18	0,15
IgG (mg/mL)	0,64	0,12	0,58	0,4	0,56	0,48	0,55	0,27	0,5	0,26	0,58	0,08

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